

ENZYME THERAPY IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. The article discusses the possibilities of using enzyme preparations for disorders of the pancreas and gastrointestinal motility in childhood. In addition, the authors draw the reader's attention to the possible causes of disorders, clinical manifestations and basic diagnostic methods for this pathology.

Keywords: pancreas, gastrointestinal tract, dysfunction, enzyme therapy, children.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the world, there has been a steady trend towards an increase in the prevalence of gastrointestinal diseases in children. At the same time, both the proportion of pathology accompanied by intestinal motility disorders and pancreatic diseases are growing. Early diagnosis and correct subsequent treatment of pancreatic diseases in children are a complex section of clinical pediatrics and gastroenterology. As is known, chronic pancreatitis is a generalized concept that unites inflammatory-dystrophic changes developing in the pancreas. Currently, the diagnosis of "reactive pancreatitis" is widely discussed, which should not be considered an independent disease, but a symptom complex that manifests itself against the background of diseases of organs functionally associated with the pancreas, or with another, combined pathology. According to modern concepts, chronic pancreatitis is an inflammatory process in the pancreas with a phased progressive course, focal or diffuse destructive and degenerative changes in the acinar tissue, duct system, with the development of functional insufficiency of varying severity with subsequent reduction in external and internal secretory function. Pancreatitis is a polyetiological disease. In childhood, it is mainly secondary [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The etiologic factors for the development of chronic pancreatitis in children include:

- pathology of the duodenum (chronic gastroduodenitis, severe motor dysfunction of the duodenum);*
- pathology of the biliary tract (abnormalities in the shape and position of the gallbladder, chronic cholecystitis, less commonly, cholelithiasis);*
- various abdominal injuries;*
- disruption of intestinal microbiocenosis (inactivation, destruction of enzymes);*
- bacterial<viral infections (epidemic mumps, hepatitis viruses, enterovirus, cytomegalovirus, herpes, mycoplasma infections, salmonellosis, infectious mononucleosis, etc.), helminthiasis (opisthorchiasis, ascariasis);*
- diseases of connective tissue, respiratory and endocrine systems (hyperlipidemia, most often types I and V, hyperparathyroidism, hypothyroidism and hypercalcemia), chronic renal failure;*
- allergic diseases, food sensitization, consumption of foods containing xenobiotics, various artificial additives and food colorings;*
- abnormalities in the development of the gland, hereditary pancreatitis, cystic fibrosis, Shwachman disease (congenital hypoplasia of the pancreas with lipomatosis), isolated deficiency of pancreatic enzymes and other hereditary diseases occurring with pancreatic insufficiency [2].*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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According to long-term observations, chronic pancreatitis in children in most cases develops secondarily. The cause of primary pancreatitis is mainly epidemic parotitis, which occurs with severe abdominal pain and a significant increase in the level of pancreatic enzymes in the blood and urine [3]. Particular attention should also be paid to impaired motility of the gastrointestinal tract in young children as one of the main etiological factors in the development of pancreatic pathology in children. At this age, these changes are mainly functional in nature and are associated with both impaired vegetative regulation of the digestive tract and immaturity of the digestive glands. In some cases, functional motility disorders pass on their own with the maturation of neural connections and humoral regulation. An example of such disorders can be functional disorders of the neonatal period: infantile intestinal colic and regurgitation. In such cases, it is advisable to carry out only symptomatic therapy aimed at relieving symptoms. However, long-term existence of motor disorders can lead to the development of an organic disease. For example, long-term duodenogastric reflux leads to the formation of reflux gastritis and, as a consequence, to chronic pancreatitis in the future. All causal factors leading to the development of a pathological process in the pancreas, it is advisable to divide into two groups. The first group includes factors that cause difficulty in the outflow of pancreatic juice and lead to ductal hypertension, the second - causes leading to direct damage to the acinar cells of the gland [9-10]. Identification of the leading etiological moment is important for the justified appointment of therapeutic measures. It has been proven that the development of any form of pancreatitis is associated with the action of several etiologic factors and ultimately leads to damage to the acinar tissue. The clinical symptoms of chronic pancreatitis in children are varied and depend on many factors: the form of the disease, the stage of development, the duration of the disease, the degree of disorder of the external and internal secretory function of the gland and concomitant disorders of other organs. However, despite the variability of the clinical manifestations of pancreatitis, several leading syndromes can be identified, the main one of which is pain. In childhood, it is possible to localize pain from primary school age, which seems difficult for diagnosis. In most children, the pain is paroxysmal and localized in the upper half of the abdomen: epigastrium, right and left hypochondrium. Sometimes the pain is constant and aching. Leading questions to the child and mother will help the pediatrician correctly choose the direction of further diagnosis. As a rule, the pain intensifies after meals and in the afternoon. Usually, the onset of a pain attack is caused by a violation of the diet (coarse, fatty, fried, sweet, cold food), significant physical exertion and a previous viral disease. Another group of symptoms characteristic of chronic pancreatitis are dyspeptic disorders. The most typical are loss of appetite, periodic vomiting at the height of the pain crisis, nausea, belching and heartburn. Changes in the intestines are manifested in the form of constipation or loose stool during the manifestation of the disease.

A significant proportion is occupied by symptoms of intoxication, asthenovegetative manifestations in the form of fatigue, frequent headaches, emotional lability, irritability. During an exacerbation, distinct pain is determined in the projection area of the head and body of the pancreas. According to research conducted at the Scientific Center for Children's Health of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences, reactive changes in the pancreas were observed in 80.8% of children with bronchial asthma, in 68% of children with celiac disease and in 38% of children suffering from gastroesophageal reflux disease. In the diagnosis of chronic pancreatitis in children, it is impossible to do without laboratory and instrumental methods, taking into account the pediatric aspect and the principles of evidence-based medicine. Recently, the definition of fecal elastase by the enzyme immunoassay has become widespread. Elastase is not destroyed during passage through the intestine and does not change

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against the background of taking pancreatic enzymes. The method is informative and highly specific, allowing to assess the degree of impairment of the exocrine function of the pancreas. The next most accessible and informative is the coprological examination of feces. In case of exocrine insufficiency, accompanied by a deficiency or decrease in the activity of pancreatic enzymes, the process of breakdown and absorption of nutrients in the intestine is disrupted, which is characterized by an increased content of neutral fat (steatorrhea), undigested muscle fibers (creatorrhea), fatty acids, soaps and starch grains in the feces.

CONCLUSION

Thus, pancreatin in the form of soluble minimicrospheres is a safe and effective drug that improves the condition of patients with dyspepsia. The effectiveness of enzymes and the adequacy of the dose are assessed by the dynamics of clinical symptoms (disappearance of pain and dyspeptic disorders), normalization of the coprogram and the level of enzymes in the duodenal contents, blood and urine, and positive dynamics of body weight. In children with a hyposecretory variant of secretion, despite clinical improvement, the need for enzyme replacement therapy may persist for several months.

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